

Additions to the knowledge of the digger wasp (Hymenoptera: Spheciformes: Crabronidae) fauna in the Fars Province of Iran

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ABSTRACT. The current paper presents new data on the distribution of 51 species of crabronid wasp (Hymenoptera: Spheciformes: Crabronidae) from the subfamilies Crabroninae (42 species of 15 genera and 5 tribes) and Pemphredoninae (9 species of 6 genera and two tribes) collected at 21 sampling sites in the Fars Province of Iran. Three species, *Tachysphex nitidus* (Spinola, 1806), *Liris memnonius* (F. Smith, 1856), and *Spilomena mocsaryi* Kohl, 1898 are newly added to the Iranian insect fauna. General distribution and Iranian localities are given for each species. The biogeographic affinities of the collected species are also discussed.

Key words: Hymenoptera, wasps, Middle East, fauna, new records, Iran

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Introduction

Crabronidae is a large, diverse and cosmopolitan family of aculeate wasps, including 8,891 species in 249 genera and 8 subfamilies (Pulawski, 2018). In the Palaearctic region, there are more than 2,000 described species of 84 genera (Antropov et al., 2017; Pulawski, 2018). There are a number of old studies on digger wasps of Iran, none of which has been conducted by a local author from the country (e.g. Radoszkowski, 1871; Gussakovskij, 1933; de Beaumont, 1957, 1970; Pulawski, 1971, 1984, 1992, 1995). The

Iranian digger wasps fauna is receiving an increasing interest in the past two decades, compensating for the long dated lack of knowledge (e.g. Ebrahimi, 2000a, 2000b, 2005, 2008, 2014; Dollfuss, 2006, 2008; Schmid-Egger, 2004; Fallahzadeh et al., 2006, 2009, 2018; Pulawski, 2007; Atbaei et al., 2015; Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015; Schmid-Egger et al., 2016; Sadeghi et al., 2016, 2018; Khosroabadi et al., 2018). Recently, Jahantigh et al. (2017) listed 315 species of Crabronidae in 56 genera and 6 subfamilies from Iran.

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The aim of the present work is to improve our knowledge of the Iranian fauna of the wasp family Crabronidae. We provide additional information on the distribution of subfamilies Crabroninae and Pemphredoninae in the Fars Province, Iran.

Material and methods

Specimens for the present study were collected by extensive sampling with Malaise traps in the Fars Province during 2015–2016. The Fars Province (coordinates 27°01'–31°51'N, 50°27'–55°45'E) is located in southern Iran, is the fifth largest province of the country, covering an area of 122,400 km², and is larger than 156 world countries (Sedaghatzadeh et al., 2012). The climate of Fars can be divided into three types: (1) north and northwest area (altitudes higher than 2000 m a. s. l.), with moderately cold winters, and mild summers; (2) central region (altitudes between 1200 and 2000 m a. s. l.), with relatively rainy mild winters, and hot dry summers; (3) south and southeast area (altitudes lower than 1200 m a. s. l.), with moderate winters and very hot summers (Sedaghatzadeh et al., 2012; Atbaei et al., 2015). Twenty-one Malaise traps were installed in 21 localities in different latitudes and altitudes, ecosystems, and used for collecting of samples (Fig. 1). Sampling localities are characterized by the data in Table 1 and shown in Figure 1. The specimens were extracted from traps and stored in 70% ethanol, then dried, pinned up, labeled, and put into collection boxes. They are deposited at the Insect Collection of Jahrom (JIAU) and Shiraz Branches (SHIAU), Islamic Azad University, Iran and the Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Sofia, Bulgaria (IBER). The list includes the following data: the valid name of the taxon, published records with local and worldwide distributions. Material examined of recorded species is presented by data for: province, city, date of

collection, number of examined specimens. Further, in order to avoid repetition in "Material examined", GPS coordinates and altitudes of sampling localities as well as the collectors of material are not given. The full information can be found in Table 1. Nomenclature follows Alexander (1992), Melo (1999), Schmid-Egger (2011, 2014), Straka & Schmid-Egger (2017), and Pulawski (2018). The general distribution was compiled from Pulawski (2018). Here, we consider the modern coastal Arabian States of Yemen, Oman and UAE as pertaining to the Afrotropical Region (See Larsen, 1984; Hölzel, 1998; Kirk-Spriggs & McGregor, 2009; Gadallah et al., 2013). The subfamilies, tribes, subtribes, genera and species are listed in alphabetic order.

Results

Family Crabronidae Latreille, 1802

Subfamily Crabroninae Latreille, 1802

Tribe Crabronini Latreille, 1802

Subtribe Crabronina Latreille, 1802

Genus *Ectemnius* Dahlbom, 1845

Ectemnius crassicornis (Spinola, 1808)

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Jahrom (loc. 20), 29.IV–30.V.2015, 1♂, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Fars (Leclercq, 1999; Dollfuss, 2004b; Jacobs, 2006; Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). – Palaearctic (Albania, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Greece, Hungary, Iraq, Israel, Italy, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Syria, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Ectemnius sexcinctus (Fabricius, 1775)

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Estahban (Gordeh) (loc. 18), 26.VII–8.VIII.2015, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: East Azerbaijan, Kermanshah (Ghazi-Soltani et al., 2010a; Ebrahimi, 2014). – Nearctic (USA); Oriental

(India, Pakistan); Palearctic (Afghanistan, Algeria, Andorra, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan,

Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Mongolia, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Tajikistan, Turkey, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Figure 1. Map of Iran and Fars Province (enlarged down in right) and location of the sampling sites. **1.** Eghlid; **2.** Noor Abad (Fahlian); **3.** Sepidan (Sar Bast); **4.** Beyza (Berekh); **5.** Marvdasht; **6.** Marvdasht (Firoozi); **7.** Faroogh; **8.** Ramjerd; **9.** Kazeroon, **10.** Kazeroon (Zavali); **11.** Siyakh; **12.** Shiraz (Ghasrodasht); **13.** Maharloo (Posht Par); **14.** Dehno; **15.** Sarvestan (Kamal Abad); **16.** Dariun; **17.** Kherameh (Dodej); **18.** Estahban (Gordeh); **19.** Estahban (Mobarak Abad); **20.** Jahrom; **21.** Khonj.

Table 1. List of the sampling localities in Fars Province.

No.	Locality	Coordinate	Altitude in m a. s. l.	Collector
01	Eghlid	30°52'42"N, 52°39'59"E	2282	M. Sadeghi
02	Noor Abad (Fahlian)	30°11'31"N, 51°29'17"E	898	M. Sadeghi
03	Sepidan (Sar Bast)	30°10'44"N, 52°02'51"E	2000	M. Sadeghi
04	Beyza (Berekh)	29°55'55"N, 52°25'41"E	1613	M. Sadeghi
05	Marvdasht	29°52'43"N, 52°48'11"E	1601	F. Farzaneh
06	Marvdasht (Firoozi)	29°55'23"N, 52°50'22"E	1615	M. Sadeghi
07	Farogh	29°58'06"N, 53°02'56"E	1675	F. Farzaneh
08	Ramjerd	29°59'41"N, 52°39'32"E	1598	M. Sadeghi
09	Kazeroon	29°40'12"N, 51°35'35"E	831	M. Sadeghi
10	Kazeroon (Zavali)	29°32'53"N, 51°46'23"E	829	M. Sadeghi
11	Siyakh	29°26'26"N, 52°25'35"E	1757	M. Sadeghi
12	Shiraz (Ghasrodasht)	29°41'46"N, 52°28'41"E	1650	M. Sadeghi
13	Maharloo (Posht Par)	29°19'08"N, 52°51'07"E	1480	M. Sadeghi
14	Dehno	28°12'06"N, 52°38'05"E	761	F. Farzaneh
15	Sarvestan (Kamal Abad)	29°17'45"N, 53°00'34"E	1757	M. Sadeghi
16	Dariun	29°33'14"N, 52°56'42"E	1740	M. Sadeghi
17	Kherameh (Dodej)	29°34'23"N, 52°59'42"E	1675	M. Sadeghi
18	Estahban (Gordeh)	29°09'53"N, 53°52'56"E	1659	M. Sadeghi
19	Estahban (Mobarak Abad)	29°15'14"N, 53°56'46"E	1573	M. Sadeghi
20	Jahrom	28°30'04"N, 53°35'16"E	1060	B. M. Jahromi
21	Khonj	27°53'31"N, 53°26'42"E	668	M. Atbaei

Genus *Lestica* Billberg, 1820***Lestica clypeata* (Schreber, 1759)**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kazeroon (Zavali) (loc. 10), 13-27.V.2016, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Alborz, Mazandaran, East Azerbaijan, Sistan & Baluchestan, Ilam, Markazi, Fars (Gussakovskij, 1933; de Beaumont, 1970; Ghazi-Soltani et al., 2009, 2010a, 2010b, 2010c, Leclercq, 1993; Ebrahimi, 2014; Atbaei et al., 2015; Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). – Palaearctic (Albania, Algeria, Andorra, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Egypt, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iraq, Israel, Italy, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lebanon, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Montenegro, Morocco, Netherlands, Norway, Palestine, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Syria, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Genus *Lindenius* Lepeletier de Saint Fargeau & Brullé, 1835***Lindenius pygmaeus armatus* (Vander Linden, 1829)**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Siyakh (loc. 11), 17-30.IX.2015, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Mazandaran, Qazvin, Tehran (de Beaumont, 1957), Fars (Atbaei et al., 2015). – Palaearctic (Albania, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bosnia, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Morocco, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Syria, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Remarks: The identification is based on de Beaumont (1956).

Tribe Oxybelini Leach, 1815**Genus *Oxybelus* Latreille, 1796*****Oxybelus dissectus elegans* Mocsáry, 1879**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Estahban (Mobarak Abad) (loc. 19), 8.VI- 6.VII.2016, 1♂; same data, 31.VII-26.VIII.2016, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Fars (Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). – Palaearctic (Hungary, Israel, Slovakia, South European Russia, Spain, Russia, Tunisia, Turkey).

Remarks: The identification is based on Guichard (1993).

***Oxybelus haemorrhoidalis* Olivier, 1812**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Khonj (loc. 21), 10-17.V.2015, 2♂♂, 1♀; same data, 6-13.IV.2015, 2♂♂, 1♀; same data, 15.V-10.VI.2015, 1♂; Kazeroon (loc. 09), 8-22.X.2015, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Isfahan, Kerman, Mazandaran, Sistan & Baluchestan, Yazd, Fars (de Beaumont, 1957, 1970; Dollfuss, 2008; Atbaei et al., 2015). – Palaearctic (Afghanistan, Algeria, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, China, Czech Republic, Egypt, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Libya, Moldova, Mongolia, Morocco, Netherlands, Portugal, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Spain, Switzerland, Syria, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

***Oxybelus lamellatus* Olivier, 1812**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Khonj (loc. 21), 10-17.V.2015, 2♂♂, 7♀♀; same data, 6-13.IV.2015, 2♂♂, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Khorasan, Qazvin, Tehran, Sistan & Baluchestan, Yazd, Fars (Gussakovskij, 1933; de Beaumont, 1957, 1970; Dollfuss, 2008; Ebrahimi, 2014; Atbaei et al., 2015). – Afrotropical (Cameroon, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Mauritania, Oman,

Somalia, Sudan, UAE); Oriental (India, Pakistan); Palaearctic (Afghanistan, Algeria, China, Cyprus, Egypt, Greece, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Kuwait, Libya, Morocco, Portugal, Saudi Arabia, Spain, Syria, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan).

Oxybelus latro Olivier, 1812

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Sarvestan (Kamal Abad) (loc. 15), 9-23.X.2015, 1♂; same data, 28.VIII-7.IX.2015, 1♀, 1♂; same data, 7-18.IX.2015, 2♀♀; same data, 28.VIII-11.IX.2015, 1♂; Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 7-19.VII.2015, 1♂; same data, 30.XI-8.XII.2016, 1♀; Dehno (loc. 14), 15-19.V.2013, 1♂; Estahban (Gordeh) (loc. 18), 23.IX-2.X.2015, 1♂; Maharloo (Posht Par) (loc. 13), 20.VIII-2.IX.2016, 1♀, 1♂; Estahban (Mobarak Abad) (loc. 19), 29.IV-20.V.2016, 1♀; same data, 31.VII-26.VIII.2016, 1♂; same data, 12.VI-4.VII.2016, 1♂; same data, 7-31.VII.2016, 2♂♂; Marvdasht (Firoozi) (loc. 06), 22.VIII-5.IX.2016, 1♂; same data, 17.VII-1.VIII.2016, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Qazvin, Tehran, Ardabil, East Azerbaijan, Khorasan Razavi, Mazandaran, Qazvin, Tehran, Fars, (de Beaumont, 1957; Ghazi-Soltani et al., 2009, 2010c; Ebrahimi, 2005, 2014; Atbaei et al., 2015; Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). - Palaearctic (Afghanistan, Albania, Algeria, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Mongolia, Morocco, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Oxybelus quatuordecimnotatus Jurine, 1807

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 3-11.IX.2015, 2♀♀; same data, 7-19.VII.2015, 1♀; same data, 15-19.V.2015, 1♀; same data, 24-29.V.2015, 1♀;

Kazeroon (loc. 09), 8-22.X.2015, 2♀♀; same data, 17-25.IX.2015, 1♀; Sarvestan (Kamal Abad) (loc. 15), 28.VIII-11.IX.2015, 1♀; same data, 28.VIII-7.IX.2015, 2♂♂; same data, 7-18.IX.2015, 1♂; Estahban (Gordeh) (loc. 18), 2-16.X.2015, 1♀; same data, 9-23.IX.2015, 1♂; Khonj (loc. 21), 10-17.V.2015, 2♂♂, 1♀; same data, 6-13.IV.2015, 2♂♂; Dehno (loc. 14), 23-28.VII.2013, 1♂; Marvdasht (Firoozi) (loc. 06), 15-29.V.2016, 2♂♂; same data, 17.VII-1.VIII.2016, 1♀; Maharloo (Posht Par) (loc. 13), 29.VIII-22.IX.2016, 1♂; same data, 20.VIII-2.IX.2016, 1♀; same data, 2-20.IX.2016, 1♀; Noor Abad (Fahlian) (loc. 02), 20.IV-6.V.2016, 2♀♀, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Isfahan, Kerman, Khorasan Razavi, Mazandaran, Qazvin, Tehran, Fars (Morice, 1921; de Beaumont, 1957, 1970; Dollfuss, 2008; Ebrahimi, 2014; Atbaei et al., 2015; Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). - Afrotropical (Oman, Yemen); Oriental (Pakistan); Palaearctic (Afghanistan, Albania, Algeria, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Libya, Moldova, Mongolia, Montenegro, Morocco, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Syria, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Oxybelus variegatus Wesmael, 1852

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Estahban (Gordeh) (loc. 18), 26.VII-8.VIII.2015, 1♂; same data, 10-21.VII.2015, 1♂, 1♀; same data, 9-23.IX.2015, 1♀; Beyza (Berekh) (loc. 04), 23.VII-5.VIII.2015, 1♂; same data, 9-19.VII.2015, 1♀; Kazeroon (loc. 09), 3-17.IX.2015, 1♂; Dehno (loc. 14), 15-19.V.2013, 1♂; same data, 19-24.VIII.2013, 1♀; Eghlid (loc. 01), 21.VIII-2.IX.2015, 1♀; same data, 8-20.VIII.2015, 1♀; Siyakh (loc. 11), 10-17.IX.2015, 1♀; Maharloo (Posht Par) (loc. 13), 29.VIII-22.IX.2016, 1♂; same data,

20. VIII-2.IX.2016, 1♂, 1♀; Kazeroon (Zavali) (loc. 10), 30.VI-19.VII.2016, 1♀; Estahban (Mobarak Abad) (loc. 19), 8.VI- 6.VII. 2016, 1♂; same data, 31.VII-26.VIII.2016, 1♀; same data, 6.VII.-16.VIII.2016, 1♀; Marvdasht (Firoozi) (loc. 06), 15-29.V.2016, 1♂; same data, 2-15.V.2016, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Isfahan, Mazandaran, Qazvin, Tehran, Fars (de Beaumont, 1957; Dollfuss, 2008; Atbaei et al., 2015; Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). - Palaearctic (Afghanistan, Austria, Belarus, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Moldova, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Syria, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Tribe Larrini Latreille, 1810

Subtribe Gastrosericina Ed. André, 1886

Genus *Gastrosericus* Spinola, 1839

Gastrosericus funereus Gussakovskij, 1931

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 7-19.VII.2015, 2♀♀; same data, 21.VIII-3.IX.2015, 1♀; Estahban (Gordeh) (loc. 18) 2-16.X.2015, 1♀; Marvdasht (Firoozi) (loc. 06), 2-15.V.2016, 1♀, 1♂; same data, 29.V-20.VI.2016, 1♀; Jahrom (loc. 20), 15-29.IV.2016, 2♀♀, 1♂; same data, 29.IV-30.V.2016, 3♀♀; Khonj (loc. 21), 20.IV-15.V.2015, 1♂; same data, 15.V-10.VI.2015, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Kerman (Pulawski, 1995), Fars (Atbaei et al., 2015; Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). - Afrotropical (Oman, UAE); Palaearctic (Egypt, Israel, Morocco, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan).

Gastrosericus waltlii Spinola, 1839

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 20-30.VII.2015, 2♂♂, 1♀; same data, 21.VIII-3.IX.2015, 2♂♂; same data, 7-19.VII.2015, 2♂♂, 1♀; same data, 29.VI-11.VII.2015, 1♂; same data, 14-26.VII.2015, 7♀♀; Marvdasht (Firoozi) (loc.

06), 2-15.V.2016, 1♂; same data, 22.VIII-5.IX.2016, 1♀; same data, 20.VI-10.VII.2016, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Kerman (Pulawski, 1995; Samin et al., 2015), Fars (Atbaei et al., 2015). - Afrotropical (Eritrea, Namibia, Oman, Sudan, UAE, Zimbabwe); Oriental (India, Sri Lanka); Palaearctic (Algeria, China, Cyprus, Egypt, France, Israel, Kazakhstan, Kuwait, Libya, Morocco, Saudi Arabia, Syria, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan).

Genus *Holotachysphex* de Beaumont, 1940

Holotachysphex holognathus (Morice, 1897)

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Jahrom (loc. 20), 29-30.V.2015, 1♀; Noor Abad (Fahlian) (loc. 02), 23.VI-10.VII.2016, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Fars (Atbaei et al., 2015; Schmid-Egger et al., 2016). - Afrotropical (Kenya, Oman, Senegal, Tanzania); Oriental (India, Sri Lanka); Palaearctic (Egypt, Greece, Israel, Saudi Arabia).

Remarks: Recently, Schmid-Egger et al. (2016) revised and keyed out all species of *Holotachysphex*.

Holotachysphex iraniensis Schmid-Egger & Fallahzadeh, 2016

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Jahrom (loc. 20), 10-22.VI.2015, 2♀♀; same data, 20-30.V.2015, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Fars, Hormozgan (Schmid-Egger et al., 2016).

Holotachysphex mochii (de Beaumont, 1947)

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Jahrom (loc. 20), 20-30.V.2015, 1♀; same data, 15-29.IV.2015, 1♂, 1♀; Kazeroon (Zavali) (loc. 10), 30.VI-19.VII.2016, 1♀; same data, 27.V-14.VI.2016, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Khorasan Razavi, Fars (Pulawski, 1992; Atbaei et al., 2015; Schmid-Egger et al. 2016). - Palaearctic (Cyprus, Greece, Israel, Jordan, Libya, Turkey, Uzbekistan).

Genus *Prosopigastra* A. Costa, 1867***Prosopigastra bulgarica* Puławski, 1958**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Beyza (Berekh) (loc. 04), 23.VII-5.VIII.2015, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Alborz (Puławski, 1979). – Palaearctic (Bulgaria, Kazakhstan, Russia (European part), Turkey).

***Prosopigastra nigra* Puławski, 1979**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 14-26.VII.2015, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Fars Province (Sadeghi et al., 2016). – Afrotropical (Niger, Mali).

Genus *Tachysphex* Kohl, 1883***Tachysphex argentatus* Gussakovskij, 1952**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 20.V-10.VI.2016, 1♀; Estahban (Mobarak Abad) (loc. 19), 6.VII - 16.VIII. 2016, 1♂; Marvdasht (Firoozi) (loc. 06), 29.V-20.VI.2016, 1♂, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Fars (Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). – Afrotropical (Eritrea, Mali, Oman, Sudan, UAE, Yemen); Palaearctic (Egypt, Israel, Kazakhstan, Syria, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan).

***Tachysphex consocius* Kohl, 1892**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Estahban (Mobarak Abad) (loc. 19), 8.VI-6.VII.2016, 1♂; same data, 12.VI-4.VII.2016, 1♀; Fars Jahrom (loc. 20), 15- 29.IV.2016, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: East Azerbaijan, Mazandaran, Fars (Puławski, 2007; Samin et al., 2015; Atbaei et al., 2015; Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). – Afrotropical (Angola, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Congo, Ethiopia, Gabon, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Mali, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Oman, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Tanzania, Togo, UAE, Uganda, Yemen, Zaire, Zambia, Zimbabwe); Oriental (Nepal, Sri Lanka); Palaearctic (Afghanistan, Algeria, Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Botswana, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Egypt, France, Greece, Hungary,

Israel, Italy, Kazakhstan, Lebanon, Libya, Morocco, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Swaziland, Syria, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkmenistan, Turkey, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

***Tachysphex fulvitaris* (A. Costa, 1867)**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Maharloo (Posht Par) (loc. 13), 13-27.V.2016, 1♀.

Distribution: Alborz, Khorasan Razavi (Puławski, 1971). – Afrotropical (Burkina Faso, South Africa, Tanzania, Zambia); Oriental (Pakistan); Palaearctic (Algeria, Austria, Belarus, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Luxembourg, Morocco, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Syria, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine).

***Tachysphex grandissimus* Gussakovskij, 1933**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 7-19.VII.2015, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Sistan & Baluchestan (Gussakovskij, 1933; Puławski, 1971). – Afrotropical (Chad, Mali, UAE); Oriental (India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka); Palaearctic (Egypt, Israel, Kazakhstan, Kuwait, Libya, Morocco, Palestine, Saudi Arabia, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkmenistan).

***Tachysphex incanus* de Beaumont, 1940**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 29.VI-11.VII.2015, 1♀; same data, 14-26.VII.2015, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Fars Province (Sadeghi et al., 2016). – Afrotropical (Mauritania); Palaearctic (Egypt, Libya).

***Tachysphex incertus* (Radoszkowski, 1877)**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 14-26.VII.2015, 1♂; same data, 20.V-10.VI.2016, 1♂; Jahrom (loc. 20), 10-22.VI.2015, 1♂; same data, 15-29.IV.2016;

Dariun (loc. 16), 8-22.IV.2016, 1♀; Sarvestan (Kamal Abad) (loc. 15), 7-18.IX.2015, 1♀; Kazeroon (Zavali) (loc. 10), 30.VI-19.VII.2016, 1♀; Estahban (Mobarak Abad) (loc. 19), 8.VI -6.VII.2016, 1♂; same data, 12.VI-4.VII.2016, 1♂, 1♀; same data, 7-31.VII.2016, 1♂; same data; 29.IV-20.V.2016, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Ardabil, Mazandaran, Golestan, Kerman, Khuzestan, East Azerbaijan, Sistan & Baluchestan, Fars ([de Beaumont, 1957](#); [Pulawski 1971](#); [Ebrahimi, 2005, 2014](#); [Atbaei et al., 2015](#); [Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015](#)). - Afrotropical (Mali, Niger, Oman); Oriental (Pakistan): Palaeartic (Algeria, Afghanistan, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Cyprus, Egypt, France, Greece, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Morocco, Palestine, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Slovakia, Spain, Syria, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Tachysphex mocsaryi Kohl, 1884

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Dehno (loc. 14), 24-29.IV.2013, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Ghom, Khorasan Razavi ([Ebrahimi, 2005, 2014](#)). - Afrotropical (Burkina Faso, Niger, Senegal); Palaeartic (Afghanistan, Algeria, Bulgaria, Hungary, Israel, Kazakhstan, Libya, Morocco, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Tachysphex nitidior de Beaumont, 1940

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Khonj (loc. 21), 15.V-10.VI.2015, 1♀; Marvdasht (Firoozi) (loc. 06), 20.VI-10.VII.2016, 1♂; Farooq (loc. 07), 17.VI- 22.VII.2015, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Kerman, Tehran, Semnan, Mazandaran, Sistan & Baluchestan, Fars ([Pulawski, 1971, 2007](#); [Atbaei et al., 2015](#); [Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015](#)). - Afrotropical (Kenya, Senegal, UAE); Oriental (India, Pakistan); Palaeartic (Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Croatia,

Cyprus, Egypt, France, Georgia, Greece, Israel, Italy, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lebanon, Libya, Mongolia, Morocco, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Spain, Switzerland, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Tachysphex nitidus (Spinola, 1806)

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 30.XI-8.XII.2015, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Fars Province (new record). - Afrotropical (Oman); Palaeartic (Bulgaria, Cyprus, China, Greece, Israel, Italy, Kazakhstan, Portugal, Russia, Spain, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan).

Tachysphex pompiliformis (Panzer, 1803)

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Estahban (Gordeh) (loc. 18), 2-6.X.2015, 1♂, Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 1-20.V.2016, 1♀; Dariun (loc. 16), 8-22.IV.2016, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Alborz, East Azerbaijan, Mazandaran, Ardabil, Khorasan Razavi, Semnan, Tehran, Fars, Kurdistan, Chahar Mahaal & Bakhtiari ([Ghahari et al., 2009](#); [Sakenin et al., 2010](#); [Ebrahimi, 2000a, 2014](#); [Atbaei et al., 2015](#)). - Nearctic (Canada, USA); Oriental (India, Pakistan,); Palaeartic (Algeria, Andorra, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kazakhstan, Korea, Latvia, Libya, Luxembourg, Mongolia, Morocco, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Remarks: *Tachysphex* is a large and cosmopolitan genus of Larrini that currently includes 453 species ([Pulawski 2018](#)). [Straka \(2005\)](#) revised *Tachysphex pompiliformis* species-group of Turkey. Recently, [Straka & Schmid-Egger \(2017\)](#) described three related species of this species-group from UAE.

***Tachysphex panzeri* (Vander Linden, 1829)**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 14-26.VII.2015, 1♂, 2♀♀; same data, 3.VII-11.VIII.2016, 1♀; Estahban (Mobarak Abad) (loc. 19), 8.VI -6.VII.2016, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Kerman, Tehran, Fars (Gussakovskij, 1933; de Beaumont, 1957; Pulawski, 1971; Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). - Afrotropical (Burkina Faso, Chad, Ethiopia, Gambia, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Oman, Sudan, UAE, Yemen); Palaearctic (Algeria, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Egypt, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Libya, Lithuania, Malta, Morocco, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan, former Yugoslavia).

***Tachysphex persa* Gussakovskij, 1933**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 14-26.VII.2015, 4♀♀; same data, 20-30.VII.2015, 2♀♀; same data, 29.VI-11.VII.2015, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Alborz, Kerman (Gussakovskij, 1933; Pulawski, 1971). Palaearctic (Israel, Kazakhstan, Turkey).

Genus *Tachytes* Panzer, 1806***Tachytes fucatus* Arnold, 1951**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Khonj (loc. 21), 6-13.IV.2015, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Fars Province (Sadeghi et al., 2016). - Afrotropical (Mali, Mauritania, UAE); Palaearctic (Egypt, Israel, Saudi Arabia).

Subtribe *Larrina* Latreille, 1810**Genus *Larra* Fabricius, 1793*****Larra arabica* Schmid-Egger, 2014**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Khonj (loc. 21), 10-17.V.2015, 1♂; Kazeroon (Zavali) (loc. 10), 30.VI -19.VII.2016, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Fars Province (Sadeghi et al., 2016). - Afrotropical (UAE); Palaearctic (Western and Central Region).

Genus *Liris* Fabricius, 1804***Liris festinans praetermissus* (Richards, 1928)**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 22-30.IX.2015, 1♂; same data, 21.VIII-3.IX.2015, 1♂, 2♀♀; same data, 14- 26.VII. 2015, 1♂; same data, 7-19.VII.2015, 1♀; Ramjerd (loc. 08), 15-20.IV.2015, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: This species was recorded from Iran without any precise locality (de Beaumont et al., 1973; Schmidt & Bitsch, 2007), Fars (Atbaei et al., 2015). - Afrotropical (Oman, UAE); Palaearctic (Afghanistan, Bulgaria, Corsica, Cyprus, France, Greece, Italy, Kazakhstan, Malta, Portugal, Spain, Turkey).

***Liris memmonius* (F. Smith, 1856)**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Khonj (loc. 21), 20.IV-15.V.2015, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Fars Province (new record). - Afrotropical (Ethiopia, Mali, South Africa); Palaearctic (Afghanistan, Egypt, Libya, Morocco).

***Liris niger* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 21.VIII- 3.IX.2015, 5♂♂, 5♀♀; same data, 14-26.VII.2015, 9♂♂, 2♀♀; same data, 20-30.VII.2015, 1♂.same data, 7-19.VII.2015, 2♂♂, 1♀; same data, 3-11.IX.2017, 1♀; same data, 30.XI-8.XII.2015, 1♀; same data, 1-20.V.2016, 1♂; Marvdasht (Firoozi) (loc. 06), 20.VI-10.VII.2016, 2♂♂, 1♀; same data, 29.V- 20.VI.2016, 1♂; Maharloo (Posht Par) (loc. 13), 17.VI-15.VII.2016, 1♀; Kazeroon (Zavali) (loc. 10), 30.VI- 19.VII. 2016, 1♀, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Alborz, Ardabil, East Azerbaijan, Sistan & Baluchestan, Bushehr, Golestan, Mazandaran, Tehran, Fars (Gussakovskij, 1933; de Beaumont, 1970;

Ghahari et al., 2009; Ghazi-Soltani et al., 2010b, 2010c; Ebrahimi, 2005, 2014; Samin et al., 2015; Atbaei et al., 2015; Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). - Afrotropical (Eritrea, Sudan, Yemen); Oriental (India, Malaysia, Sri Lanka,); Palaearctic (Afghanistan, Albania, Algeria, Austria, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Cyprus, Egypt, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Libya, Malta, Mongolia, Morocco, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Remarks: Recently, character variation in *L. niger* was discussed by Atbaei et al. (2015).

Liris nigricans (Walker, 1871)

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 21.VIII- 3.IX.2015, 1♀; same data, 30.XI-8.XII.2015, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Gilan (Morice, 1921), Fars (Atbaei et al., 2015; Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). - Afrotropical (Central African Republic, Chad, Ethiopia, Madagascar, Oman, Tanzania, UAE, Yemen, Zaire); Palaearctic (Afghanistan, Algeria, Canary Islands, China, Cyprus, Egypt, Iraq, Israel, Kazakhstan, Libya, Morocco, Spain, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkey, Uzbekistan).

Tribe Miscophini W. Fox, 1895

Genus *Miscophus* Jurine, 1807

Miscophus bicolor Jurine, 1807

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Khonj (loc. 21), 20.IV-15.V.2015, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Tehran (de Andrade, 1960), Fars (Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). - Palaearctic (Algeria, Andorra, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Egypt, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan, Korea, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland,

Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Syria, Turkey, Ukraine).

Miscophus helveticus Kohl, 1883

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 14-26.VII.2015, 1♀; same data, 7-19.VII.2015, 1♀; same data, 1-20.V.2016, 1♀; Estahban (Gordeh) (loc. 18), 29.IV-20.V.2016, 1♀; Marvdasht (Firoozi) (loc. 06), 5-30 IX.2016, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Fars Province (Sadeghi et al., 2016). - Afrotropical (UAE); Palaearctic (Croatia, Cyprus, France, Hungary, Italy, Israel, Malta, Portugal, Russia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey).

Miscophus mimeticus Honoré, 1944

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 14-26.VII.2015, 3♂♂, 4♀♀; same data, 29.VI-11.VII.2015, 2♀♀; same data, 7- 19.VII.2015, 4♀♀; Estahban (Gordeh) (loc. 18), 8.VI- 6.VII.2016, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Fars (Atbaei et al., 2015). - Afrotropical (UAE); Palaearctic (Egypt, Kazakhstan, Mongolia).

Genus *Solierella* Spinola, 1851

Solierella compedita (Piccioli, 1869)

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 21.VIII-3.IX 2015, 1♂, 1♀; same data, 29.VI-11.VII.2015, 2♀♀; same data, 14- 26.VII.2015, 5♀♀; same data, 7-19.VII. 2015, 5♀♀; Estahban (Gordeh) (loc. 18), 10- 21.VII.2015, 1♀; Kazeroon (Zavali) (loc. 10), 30.VI-19.VII.2016, 8♀♀, 11♂♂; same data, 1-25.VII.2016, 1♂; same data, 23.VIII-22.IX.2016, 3♂♂, 1♀; same data, 19.VII.-23.VIII.2016, 1♂, 10♀♀; 13-27.V.2016, 1♂, 1♀; Khonj (loc. 21), 20.IV-15.V.2015, 2♂♂, 1♀; same data, 10.VI-7.VII.2015, 1♀; Jahrom (loc. 20), 29-30.V.2015, 1♂; same data, 15-29.IV2016, 1♂, 1♀; Noor Abad (Fahlian) (loc. 02), 20.IV-6.V.2016, 1♀; Maharloo (Posht Par) (loc. 13), 27.V-17.VI.2016, 1♂; Marvdasht (Firoozi) (loc. 06), 20.VI-10.VII.2016, 1♀; same data, 5-30.IX.2016, 1♂;

Estahban (Mobarak Abad) (loc. 19), 8.VI-6.VII.2016, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Fars (Atbaei et al., 2015). - Palaearctic (Albania, Algeria, Austria, Bulgaria, Canary Islands, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Malta, Morocco, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine).

Remarks: Recently, comments on distribution and variation of certain morphological characters of *S. compedita* were given by Atbaei et al. (2015). The species of Palaearctic *Solierella* are currently under revision by Schmid-Egger (Schmid-Egger, personal communication).

Solierella verhoeffi de Beaumont, 1964

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 14-26.VII.2015, 1♀; Kazeroon (Zavali) (loc. 10), 30.VI-19.VII.2016, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Fars Province (Sadeghi et al., 2016). - Palaearctic (Cyprus, Greece, Israel, Spain, Turkey).

Tribe Trypoxylini Lepeletier de Saint Fargeau, 1845

Genus *Pison* Jurine, 1808

Pison sericeum Kohl, 1888

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 7-19.VII.2015, 1♂; same data, 14-26.VII.2015, 2♀♀.

Distribution: Iran: Fars (Atbaei et al., 2015). - Palaearctic (Bulgaria, Greece, Israel, Italy, Russia, Turkey).

Genus *Trypoxylon* Latreille, 1796

Trypoxylon scutatatum Chevrier, 1867

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Dehno (loc. 14), 15-20.VII.2013, 1♂; same data, 3-11.IX.2013, 1♂; Sarvestan (Kamal Abad) (loc. 15), 28.VIII-7.IX.2015, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Alborz, East Azerbaijan, Mazandaran, Ardabil, Fars (de Beaumont, 1957; Ghazi-Sotani et al., 2010b, 2010c; Ebrahimi, 2005, 2014; Atbaei et al., 2015; Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). - Afrotropical (Ethiopia); Palaearctic (Afghanistan, Algeria, Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Israel, Italy, Kazakhstan, Libya, Morocco, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Spain, Switzerland, Syria, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Subfamily Pemphredoninae Dahlbom, 1835

Tribe Pemphredonini Dahlbom, 1835

Subtribe Pemphredonina Dahlbom, 1835

Genus *Diodontus* Curtis, 1834

Diodontus minutus (Fabricius, 1793)

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Marvdasht (loc. 05), 8-12.IV.2013, 1♂, 3♀♀; same data, 5-30.IX.2016, 1♀; same data, 29.V-20.VI.2016, 1♀; same data, 20.VI-10.VII.2016, 1♀; Khonj (loc. 21), 10-17.V.2015, 1♂; same data, 15.V-10.VI.2015, 1♀; same data, 10.VI-7.VII.2015, 1♀; Kherameh (Dodej) (loc. 17), 22-30.IX.2015, 4♀♀; same data, 21.VIII-3.IX.2015, 7♀♀; same data, 3-11.IX.2015, 8♀♀; same data, 7-19.VII.2015, 4♀♀; same data, 30.XI-8.XII.2015, 1♂, 2♀♀; same data, 1-20.V.2016, 1♀; Maharloo (Posht Par) (loc. 13), 22.IX-29.VIII.2015, 1♂, 8♀♀; same data, 2-20.IX.2016, 1♂; Noor Abad (Fahlian) (loc. 02), 20.IV-6.V.2016, 2♀♀; Jahrom (loc. 20), 29.IV-30.V.2016, 3♀♀; same data, 15-29.IV.2016, 4♀♀; Estahban (Mobarak Abad) (loc. 19), 29.IV-20.V.2016, 1♀; Kazeroon (Zavali) (loc. 10), 23.VIII-22.IX.2016, 1♀; same data, 30.VI-19.VII.2016, 2♀♀; Shiraz (Ghasrodasht) (loc. 12), 24.IV-20.V.2016, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Alborz, Khorasan Razavi, Tehran, Fars (Gussakovskij, 1933; Ebrahimi, 2014; Atbaei et al., 2015; Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). - Afrotropical (Sudan);

Nearctic (Canada, USA); Palaearctic (Afghanistan, Albania, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iraq, Israel, Italy, Kazakhstan, Korea, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Malta, Mongolia, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Syria, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Genus *Passaloeus* Shuckard, 1837

***Passaloeus gracilis* (Curtis, 1834)**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Shiraz (Ghasrodasht) (loc. 12), 24.VIII-8.IX 2015, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Tehran (Ebrahimi, 2005, 2014). - Nearctic (USA); Palaearctic (Austria, Andorra, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canary Islands, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Morocco, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

***Passaloeus pictus* Ribaut, 1952**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Sepidan (Sar Bast) (loc. 03), 21.VII-2.VIII.2015, 1♂. Shiraz (Ghasrodasht) (loc. 12), 24.VIII-8.IX.2015, 1♀; Maharloo (Posht Par) (loc. 13), 29.VIII-22.IX.2016, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Fars (Atbaei et al., 2015; Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). - Neotropical (Brazil, introduced in Sao Paulo); Palaearctic (Algeria, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Morocco, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia,

Spain, Switzerland, Syria, Turkey, Ukraine).

Genus *Pemphredon* Latreille, 1796

***Pemphredon lethifer* (Shuckard, 1837)**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Beyza (Berekh) (loc. 04), 23.VII- 5.VIII.2015, 1♀; Noor Abad (Fahlian) (loc. 02), 20.IV-6.V.2016, 3♀♀.

Distribution: Iran: Isfahan, Alborz, Qazvin, Tehran, Fars (Dollfuss, 1995; Ebrahimi, 2005, 2014; Atbaei et al., 2015; Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015). - Nearctic (USA); Palaearctic (Afghanistan, Algeria, Andorra, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, China, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iraq, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Kyrgyzstan, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Mongolia, Morocco, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Tajikistan, Turkey, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Subtribe *Spilomenina* Shuckard, 1838

Genus *Spilomena* Shuckard, 1838

***Spilomena roshanica* Gussakovskij, 1952**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Jahrom (loc. 20), 10-22.VI.2015, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Fars (Atbaei et al., 2015). - Palaearctic (Kazakhstan, Tajikistan).

***Spilomena mocsaryi* Kohl, 1898**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Jahrom (loc. 20), 15-29.IV.2015, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Fars Province (new record). - Afrotropical (UAE); Palaearctic (Austria, Bulgaria, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan, Poland, Russia, Spain, Switzerland, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan).

Tribe Psenini A. Costa, 1858**Genus *Mimumesa* Malloch, 1933*****Mimumesa unicolor* (Vander Linden, 1829)**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Dehno (loc. 14), 24-29.V.2013, 1♀; Sarvestan (Kamal Abad) (loc. 15), 28.VIII-7.IX.2015, 1♀; Faroogh (loc. 07, 1672 m), 17.VI-22.VII.2015, 1♂.

Distribution: Iran: Fars ([Atbaei et al., 2015](#)). – Oriental (Pakistan); Palaearctic (Afghanistan, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iraq, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan).

Genus *Psenulus* Kohl, 1896***Psenulus meridionalis* de Beaumont, 1937**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Faroogh (loc. 07), 22-27 IV.2015, 3♂♂; Marvdasht (Firoozi) (loc. 06), 15-25.VII.2015, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Alborz, Tehran, Fars ([Dollfuss, 2004a](#); [Ebrahimi, 2005, 2014](#)). – Palaearctic (Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iraq, Italy, Jordan, Poland, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Syria, Turkey, Ukraine).

***Psenulus pan* de Beaumont, 1967**

Material examined: IRAN: Fars: Kazeroon (loc. 09), 27.X-12.XI. 2015, 1♀.

Distribution: Iran: Fars ([Dollfuss, 2004a](#); [Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015](#)). – Palaearctic (Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran, Kazakhstan, Lebanon, Syria, Turkey).

Discussion

During the present study, 399 specimens have been collected, including 153 males

and 246 females. Fifty-one species and 21 genera are listed. Of the 21 genera, *Tachysphex* with 12 species is the most rich-species. Three species, *Tachysphex nitidus*, *Liris memnonius* and *Spilomena mocsaryi* are recorded for the first time from Iran.

The biogeographic location of Iran in the Palaearctic Region is unique, at the crossroads of the Oriental and Afrotropical ecozones, Central Asia and Caucasus. Therefore, its fauna is expected to be mainly Western Palaearctic, but with the possible representation of Central Asian, Caucasian, Oriental and Afro-tropical elements ([Strumia & Fallahzadeh, 2015](#)). Based on the collected specimens, the following geographic analysis can be presented. One species (1.97%) is only known from Iran, whereas the highest number of species (17 species, 33.33%) is restricted to the Palaearctic region. In addition, nine species (17.64%) are mainly distributed in three biogeographic areas, the Palaearctic, Afrotropical and Oriental regions, but are not truly cosmopolitan. Moreover, three species (5.88%) are distributed in the Holarctic region. There is a slight overlap with the fauna of the Oriental region (one species, 1.97%), while 39.21% (20 species) overlap with the Afrotropical region. Currently, no data are available about overlapping with the Australasian region.

Iran apparently has a complex fauna influenced by different geographical zones. However, there is no comprehensive research or summarizing study about this family from Iran and thus study of this fauna is not easy ([Rezaei & Fallahzadeh, 2015](#)). We assume the insect fauna in southern Iran has not been completely explored yet. Further inventory of Iranian digger wasps and the revisionary works on some crabronid wasp taxa are recommended.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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معرفی بخش بیشتری از فون زنبورهای خانواده Crabronidae (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Spheciformes) از استان فارس، ایران

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چکیده: در مقاله حاضر، اطلاعات جدیدی از پراکنش ۵۱ گونه از زنبورهای خانواده Crabronidae (Hymenoptera: Spheciformes) ارائه می‌شود. گونه‌های متعلق به دو زیر خانواده Crabroninae (۴۲ گونه متعلق به ۱۵ جنس و ۵ طایفه) و Pemphredoninae (۹ گونه متعلق به ۶ جنس و دو طایفه) می‌باشند که از ۲۱ منطقه استان فارس جمع‌آوری شدند. در میان نمونه‌های جمع‌آوری شده، سه گونه *Liris memnonius* (F. Smith, 1856)، *Tachysphex nitidus* (Spinola, 1806) و *Spilomena mocsaryi* Kohl, 1898 برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شوند. پراکنش گونه‌ها در ایران و سایر کشورها ارائه شده و انتشار بیوجغرافیایی آنها مورد بحث قرار گرفته است.

واژگان کلیدی: بال‌غشائیان، زنبور، خاورمیانه، فون، گزارش‌های جدید، ایران